

Communication-Aware Dynamic Speed Control for Interference Mitigation in 6G Mobile Subnetworks

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Abstract—6G subnetworks may be installed in mobile entities such as robots navigating the factory floor in proximity. The potential high density of the subnetworks may result in interference limitation. Conventional interference mitigation approaches such as transmit power control achieve limited gain due to strong mutual interference when the subnetworks are nearby. Hence, an approach to mitigate interference by controlling the proximity of the mobile subnetworks may be required. In this paper, we study the potential of communication-aware dynamic speed control for interference mitigation in mobile subnetworks. The adjustment of the target speed of the mobile robots to minimize travel time is constrained by the minimum signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR) requirement of their subnetwork. We propose a communication-aware speed control policy trained with reinforcement learning based on proximal policy optimization. With thorough simulation, we show that the method can effectively mitigate interference by controlling the proximity of the mobile subnetworks while incurring only a minor increase in average travel time compared to when the control is unaware of the communication requirement. It significantly improves the probability of achieving the stringent minimum SINR requirement from 75% to more than 95%.

Index Terms—Interference mitigation, dynamic speed control, mobile subnetworks, 6G, reinforcement learning, proximal policy optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future 6G networks are anticipated to incorporate short-range, low-power cells called subnetworks at the edge to facilitate high-performance wireless connectivity between devices inside entities, replacing traditional wired connections [1], [2]. These entities may be vehicles, industrial machines, mobile robots, multi-robot swarms, humans, and the like [3]. The authors in [3] outlined the primary technology components of the 6G subnetworks. They also emphasized the interference limitation of subnetworks due to their potential high density. For example, in scenarios with multiple subnetworks nearby, such as subnetworks in robots (mobile subnetworks) navigating a common area on the factory floor as illustrated in Figure 1.

Many studies, including [4], [5], have addressed interference mitigation in mobile subnetworks using traditional methods

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Fig. 1: Each mobile robot carries a subnetwork to facilitate the wireless communication between devices in the robot. There is strong mutual interference between the subnetworks due to the proximity of the robots on the factory floor.

such as transmit power control and frequency channel allocation. However, the efficacy of these conventional approaches is inherently limited in highly dense scenarios. The work in [4] proposed a multi-agent soft-actor critic reinforcement learning (RL) approach for optimizing joint transmit power and channel allocation in mobile subnetworks in factory settings. While transmit power control and channel allocation are viable conventional methods for inter-cell interference mitigation, their efficacy diminishes with increased density due to strong mutual interference. For example, in [4], the authors show a rapid decline in the gain in transmission rate as the number of mobile subnetworks increases from 4 to 20 in the same factory area. To tackle this limitation, this study investigates a novel approach, communication-aware dynamic speed control to mitigate interference in mobile subnetworks.

Communication-aware dynamic speed control is inspired by previous works on communication-aware motion planning [6]–[9]. This involves planning the robot’s trajectory to achieve the robotics task while considering specific communication metrics. It is becoming increasingly important as new wireless concepts emerge, such as robotic-assisted communication

(RaC) like UAV communication, and communication-assisted robotics (CaR) [6]. An example of CaR is the case of subnetworks in mobile robots. The work in [7] investigated communication-aware trajectory planning for a mobile robot. Their goal was to optimize the trajectory to minimize the energy used by the robot while maintaining good wireless channel conditions between the robot and the base station. Similarly, the work in [8] devised a communication-aware motion planning policy to enhance the likelihood of a mobile robot maintaining connectivity with the stationary base station while carrying out a sensing task.

In this study, we consider a scenario involving subnetworks installed in mobile robots that navigate a shared factory environment as shown in Figure 1. The subnetwork comprises devices, such as wireless sensors, actuators, and controllers associated with the mobile robot, and an access point to facilitate intra-robot communication tasks. The communication tasks are crucial for operations such as closed-loop control or data gathering during the robot's navigation. However, due to the presence of multiple robots in proximity, there may be strong mutual interference between the subnetworks sharing limited radio resources. This interference can diminish the signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR) of the intra-subnetwork communication, causing transmission errors that would affect the successful completion of the intra-robot communication tasks. We consider addressing this challenge by devising a communication-aware dynamic speed control policy. The policy is designed to control the speed of the mobile robots considering two goals: 1) To ensure that the robots can complete their navigation tasks, such as reaching their destination in the stipulated time. 2) To minimize interference in order to achieve highly reliable intra-subnetwork communication. Our approach differs from the current state-of-the-art, such as the works in [4], [5], which focus on optimizing transmit power and channel allocation for interference mitigation. These approaches have been shown to offer limited gain in highly dense scenarios [4]. To our knowledge, this is the first study on communication-aware dynamic speed control for interference mitigation in mobile subnetworks. Our contributions are as follows:

- We formulate a joint optimization problem aimed at adjusting the speed of the mobile robots to minimize the travel time while maintaining compliance with a minimum SINR constraint for successful intra-subnetwork communication.
- We propose an RL approach using proximal policy optimization to solve the optimization problem.
- Through extensive numerical simulations, we demonstrate that our approach can significantly increase the probability of achieving the SINR target compared to classical transmit power control algorithms, which fail due to high density.

The rest of the paper is as follows. In the next section, we describe the system model of the mobile subnetworks including the communication and control system, and the

problem statement. Section III describes the proposed RL algorithm to solve the problem. Section IV discusses the results, and section V presents the conclusion and outlook.

II. MOBILE SUBNETWORKS SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider N mobile robots navigating a preplanned trajectory as shown in Figure 1. Each robot carries a wireless subnetwork, hence we have N subnetworks sharing the same radio resources. Effective communication between the devices and the AP within the subnetwork necessitates a minimum SINR. However, the achievable SINR is limited by interference since the subnetwork operates on the same radio resources. Our objective is to ensure that the mobile robots reach their destination within the stipulated time while fulfilling the SINR requirement for intra-subnetwork (intra-robot) communication.

A. Intra-Subnetwork Communication Model

We consider transmission between a device in subnetwork $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ transmitting with a fixed power p_{T_n} over a desired channel of gain $h_n^{(t)}$ at time t . The transmission is interfered with by a device in subnetwork $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, N \mid m \neq n\}$ transmitting with a transmit power p_{T_m} over an interference channel with gain $h_{m,n}^{(t)}$. The SINR can be modelled as

$$\text{SINR}_n^{(t)} = \frac{p_{T_n} h_n^{(t)}}{\sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq n}}^N p_{T_m} h_{m,n}^{(t)} + \sigma^2}, \quad (1)$$

where σ^2 is the noise power. The desired link channel gain, $h_n^{(t)} = f(\zeta_n^{(t)}, d_n, \rho_n, f_c)$ is a function of the small scale fading $\zeta_n^{(t)}$, the distance between the device and the AP in the subnetwork, d_n , the shadowing ρ_n , and centre frequency f_c . Similarly, the interfering link channel gain, $h_{m,n}^{(t)} = f(\zeta_{m,n}^{(t)}, d_{m,n}^{(t)}, \rho_{m,n}^{(t)}, f_c)$ is a function of the small scale fading $\zeta_{m,n}^{(t)}$, the distance between the device in subnetwork m and the AP in subnetwork n , $d_{m,n}^{(t)}$, and shadowing $\rho_{m,n}^{(t)}$. It is important to note that with all factors constant, as the distance increases, the channel gain decreases. Therefore, by increasing the distance $d_{m,n}^{(t)}$, we can reduce the interference term $p_{T_m} h_{m,n}^{(t)}$ and increase $\text{SINR}_n^{(t)}$ in (1).

We assume the intra-subnetwork communication is expected to support ultra-reliable low latency service (URLLC) with the transmission of small packets. Hence, we model the communication error using the BLER model from the finite-blocklength information theory in [10]. Given the SINR, channel bandwidth, B , and latency constraint, τ , the number of channel uses $\psi = 2B\tau$ [10]. For the transmission of a packet of b (bits), the block error rate (BLER) for $1/2$ code rate is [10]

$$\text{BLER}_n^{(t)} = Q \left(\frac{\frac{\psi}{2} \log_2 \left(1 + \text{SINR}_n^{(t)} \right) - b + \frac{1}{2} \log_2 \psi}{\sqrt{\psi V \left(\text{SINR}_n^{(t)} \right)}} \right), \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2: Mobility model of the robot. The state consists of the lateral error e , the yaw angular error θ , their derivatives and the velocity error v .

where

$$V(\text{SINR}_n^{(t)}) = \frac{\text{SINR}_n^{(t)}(\text{SINR}_n^{(t)} + 2)}{2(\text{SINR}_n^{(t)} + 1)^2} \log_2^2 e \quad (3)$$

is the channel dispersion.

B. Mobility Model

The subnetwork is installed in a mobile robot navigating a target course as shown in Figure 2. The state \mathbf{x} of the mobile robot consists of the lateral error from the trajectory point e , the yaw angular error θ , their derivatives $\dot{e}, \dot{\theta}$ and the error between the vehicle's current speed and a target speed (\bar{v}), v i.e. $\mathbf{x} = [e, \dot{e}, \theta, \dot{\theta}, v]'$, where $'$ denotes vector transpose operation. The mobile robot moves based on linear acceleration a meant to compensate for speed and lateral error, and angular acceleration δ to correct the error in orientation, hence the action $\mathbf{u} = [\delta, a]'$. The mobile robot has a state transition matrix \mathbf{A} and action response matrix \mathbf{B} , hence we can define the linearized state transition of the mobile robot n from time t to $t + 1$ as [11]

$$\mathbf{x}_n^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{A}_n \mathbf{x}_n^{(t)} + \mathbf{B}_n \mathbf{u}_n^{(t)}. \quad (4)$$

The optimal action aims to reduce the state error to zero subject to maximum acceleration constraint. We implement the optimal action using a linear quadratic regulator (LQR) controller. Interested readers can consult [11] for more details on mobile robot control using an LQR controller.

C. Problem Statement

The communication-aware dynamic speed control for mobile subnetworks involves solving an optimization problem to achieve the robotics task key performance indicator (KPI) while ensuring that a minimum level of intra-subnetwork communication KPI is met. In this study, we consider that the robotics task KPI is the travel time of the mobile robot which should be minimized, and the intra-subnetwork communication KPI is an SINR constraint. The SINR constraint is the minimum SINR required to enable reliable communication between devices and the access point in the subnetwork. This is necessary for critical communication tasks such as closed-loop control or efficient data gathering. To minimize travel time, the mobile robot should move at the maximum allowable speed, hence the target speed, $\bar{v} = v_{\max}$. However, to meet stringent SINR requirements, it is important to minimize

interference. This can be achieved by increasing the distance $d_{m,n}$ between interfering neighbours, as mentioned in section II-A. One way to increase the distance between interfering neighbours is by increasing one's speed while decreasing the other's speed. This can be accomplished by allocating different target speeds $\bar{v} \leq v_{\max}$. Hence, we consider our optimization variables to be the target speed, $\bar{v}_n^{(t)} \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$. We then define the optimization problem as that of finding the series of target speed $\bar{v}_n^{(t)}$ to maximize the difference between the target velocity and the maximum velocity subject to constraints on SINR, $\text{SINR}_{n,\min}$ and maximum speed as in

$$\text{maximize}_{\bar{v}_1^{(t)}, \bar{v}_2^{(t)}, \dots, \bar{v}_N^{(t)}} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \|\bar{v}_n^{(t)} - v_{\max}\|, \quad (5a)$$

subject to

$$\text{SINR}_n^{(t)} \geq \text{SINR}_{n,\min}, \quad (5b)$$

$$v_{\min} < \bar{v}_n^{(t)} \leq v_{\max} \quad (5c)$$

Remark 1: In this work, we assume a pre-planned trajectory and a pre-designed LQR controller which controls the movement of the robot given the target trajectory and target speed as stated in section II-B. Therefore, our problem definition and solution only focus on adjusting the target speed in response to perceived interference that could violate the SINR constraint.

III. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING SOLUTION USING PROXIMAL POLICY OPTIMIZATION

We consider a model-free RL approach to solve the optimization problem in (5), which is suitable for dynamic problems. This involves conceptualizing the problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), which characterizes the interaction between an agent and its environment to maximize a cumulative reward function. The components of an MDP include observation space, action space, agent, environment, and reward function [12]. The observation space represents all possible states, while the action space includes all possible actions an agent can take in an environment. The agent's policy denoted as $\pi_\theta(\mathbf{a}^{(t)}|\mathbf{s}^{(t)})$ with trainable parameter θ is formulated to select actions \mathbf{a} that optimize a reward function [12] given the current observation \mathbf{s} . The reward function is designed considering the objectives and constraints specified in (5). The goal of the agent is to learn a policy that maximizes cumulative reward over time. We apply the Actor-critic-based Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) approach [13]. PPO is suitable for both discrete and continuous observation and action spaces, and it is renowned for enhanced stability and efficiency compared to most RL algorithms [13]. The Actor-Critic framework consists of an actor network and a critic network. The actor determines actions based on the current observation, and the critic evaluates the actions by estimating the value function.

A. Observation and Action Space

We describe the observation $\mathbf{s}^{(t)}$ of the mobile subnetworks to include some variables related to (5) $\mathbf{s}^{(t)} =$

$\{h_n^{(t)}, h_{m,n}^{(t)}, v_n^{(t)}, \text{SINR}_n; \forall n, m \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, m \neq n\}$ which are continuous. The actions $\mathbf{a}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^N \in [0, 1]$ are continuous values between 0 and 1. However, this is scaled by the maximum speed to result in the target speed for each mobile subnetwork, $\bar{v}_n^{(t)} \in [0, v_{max}]$.

B. Reward Function

To train the RL agent to solve the problem in (5), we must design the reward function to reflect the objective and the constraints. Since the objective is to maximize the difference $\bar{v}_n^{(t)} - v_{max}$ subject to the SINR constraint (5b) we define the reward \mathcal{R} as

$$\mathcal{R}^{(t)} = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\|\bar{v}_n^{(t)} - v_{max}\| - \mathcal{R}_{\text{SINR}_n}^{(t)} \right), \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{SINR}_n}^{(t)} = \begin{cases} K > 0, & \text{if } \text{SINR}_n^{(t)} < \text{SINR}_{n,\min} \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The reward function (6) shows that the advantage of allocating the maximum speed as the target speed is penalized by $\mathcal{R}_{\text{SINR}_n}^{(t)}$, which is a positive constant term K when the intra-subnetwork SINR is less than the minimum SINR threshold as in (7). If $\text{SINR}_{n,\min} = 0$ or $K = 0$, then the optimal reward is to allocate the maximum speed as the target speed. However, when $\text{SINR}_{n,\min} > 0$, the larger the value of K the higher the penalty for violating the minimum SINR constraint. Also, from (6) and (7), the maximum value of $\mathcal{R}^{(t)}$ is 0.

C. Policy Actor and Critic Network

The policy actor $\pi_\theta(\mathbf{a}^{(t)}|\mathbf{s}^{(t)})$ and the policy critic $V_\phi(\mathbf{s}^{(t)})$ are fully connected neural networks with trainable parameters θ and ϕ , respectively. The actor neural network takes the flattened array of observations as input. It outputs the mean of actions $\mathbf{a}_{mean}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ using a hyperbolic tangent activation function at the output layer. $\mathbf{a}^{(t)}$ is then sampled from N independent Gaussian distributions with a mean of $\mathbf{a}_{mean}^{(t)}$ and a standard deviation value, ϱ , i.e. $\mathbf{a}^{(t)}[n] \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{a}_{mean}^{(t)}[n], \varrho)$. The ϱ value is decayed from a high value towards 0 during the training procedure to enable exploration. The critic neural network equally takes the flattened array of observations as an input and outputs the value of the state using a tangent activation function at the output layer.

D. Training via Proximal Policy Optimization

The PPO algorithm is used to train the communication-aware dynamic speed control policy. Algorithm 1 shows the training procedure. First, the actor neural network, $\pi_\theta(\cdot)$, and the critic neural network $V_\phi(\cdot)$ are initialized. At each time step, the agent receives the observation centrally from all the mobile subnetworks and takes action (target velocity) using the actor policy $\pi_\theta(\mathbf{a}^{(t)}|\mathbf{s}^{(t)})$. The target velocities are sent to the corresponding mobile robots which navigate the environment. The corresponding transition $(\mathbf{s}^{(t)}, \mathbf{a}^{(t)}, \mathcal{R}^{(t)}, \mathbf{s}^{(t+1)})$ is stored in a buffer. Once the agent has gathered sufficient experience, it performs updates on both the actor and critic networks. To update the critic network, the value loss $L_{\text{value}}(\phi) =$

$\mathbb{E} (R^{(t)} - V_\phi(\mathbf{s}^{(t)}))^2$, which represents the difference between the predicted value and the actual discounted cumulative return is minimized. Where $R^{(t)} = \mathcal{R}^{(t)} + \gamma\mathcal{R}^{(t+1)} + \gamma^2\mathcal{R}^{(t+2)} + \dots$, represents the discounted return with a discount factor γ .

To update the actor neural network, PPO uses a clipped surrogate objective, $L_{\text{clip}}(\theta)$ to ensure the new policy does not deviate significantly from the old policy which may cause large updates that might destabilize training. $L_{\text{clip}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E} [\min(\pi'_\theta A^{(t)}, \text{clip}(\pi'_\theta, 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) A^{(t)})]$, where $A^{(t)} = R^{(t)} - V_\phi(\mathbf{s}^{(t)})$ is the advantage function, $\pi'_\theta = \pi_\theta(\mathbf{a}^{(t)}|\mathbf{s}^{(t)})/\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(\mathbf{a}^{(t)}|\mathbf{s}^{(t)})$ is the probability ratio between the new and old policies. The clipping function prevents large updates by limiting this ratio between $1 - \epsilon$ and $1 + \epsilon$. ϵ is a small hyperparameter controlling the allowable update size. During training, the standard deviation of the action distribution denoted ϱ , is initially set to a higher value to encourage exploration. As training progresses, the standard deviation is gradually reduced using a linear decay, i.e. $\varrho^{(t+1)} = \max(\varrho_{\min}, \varrho^{(t)} - \alpha)$, where α is the decay rate and ϱ_{\min} is the minimum allowable standard deviation. This gradual reduction encourages the agent to shift from exploration to exploitation over time. The training process continues until the predefined maximum number of time steps is reached. Throughout the process, the actor and critic networks are updated using the experiences stored in the buffer, ensuring that the policy is gradually optimized while maintaining stability.

Algorithm 1 PPO Training Process

- 1: **Initialize:**
 - 2: Initialize *environment*, initialize actor-network $\pi_\theta(\cdot)$, critic network $V_\phi(\cdot)$, ϱ , set *time step* = 0, define *max training timesteps*, ϵ , γ , ϱ_{\min} , *max training timesteps*.
 - 3: **while** *time step* \leq *max training timesteps* **do**
 - 4: **for** $t = 1$ to *max episode length* **do**
 - 5: Run old $\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(\cdot)$ to take action
 - 6: Collect transition and append in buffer
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **if** *update time* **then**
 - 9: **Update Actor-Critic Networks:**
 - 10: Compute discounted rewards and advantages
 - 11: Normalize the advantages
 - 12: Minimize the value loss
 - 13: Optimize the clipped objective function
 - 14: **end if**
 - 15: **end while**
-

E. Execution Procedure

We assume the agent is deployed in an edge server on the factory's central network. At specified intervals, each subnetwork AP obtains its state information, including the channel gain of the desired and interfering link, current error in velocity and the SINR. The state information is transmitted to the agent in the factory's central network which uses the optimized communication-aware dynamic speed control policy

TABLE I: Simulation Assumption

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Factory area	30m x 30m	Number of mobile subnetworks	10
Subnetwork radius	1m	Number of devices per subnetwork	1
Max speed	2m/s	Travel distance	25m
clutter density, clutter size	0.2, 2m	Correlation distance	10m
Shadowing std (LOS, NLOS)	4dB, 5.7dB	Path loss exponent (LOS, NLOS)	2.15, 2.55
Maximum transmit power, Pmax	0 dBm	Bandwidth	1.3 MHz
Data size	32 bytes	Center frequency	10 GHz
Noise figure	10 dB	Traffic/Sampling interval, dt	20ms
Traffic type	Periodic	Latency	0.5ms

to determine and communicate the required target speed to each mobile subnetwork.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Simulation Settings and Benchmarks

We consider 10 mobile subnetworks with a maximum speed of 2 m/s. The mobile robots each carrying a subnetwork are assigned tasks to travel 25 m along parallel tracks 2.5 m apart on the factory floor similar to Figure 1. We adopt the 3GPP path loss model for indoor factory scenarios considering sparse-clutter low antenna scenarios to model the communication links path loss, $PL(\cdot)$ [14] with the shadowing spatially correlated according to a two-dimensional Gaussian random process [5]. The small-scale fading is sampled from a complex-valued Rayleigh distribution, $\zeta \sim \mathcal{CN}(0,1)$ and the time-domain correlation is modelled using Jake's Doppler model. The channel gain is then calculated as $h = \zeta \times \sqrt{10^{PL/10}}$. To derive $SINR_{min}$, we assume each subnetwork supports a URLLC between a device and the AP. The device transmits 32 bytes of data over a 1.3 MHz channel. The BLER target $\approx 10^{-6}$ and latency = 0.5 ms. This yields $SINR_{min} \approx 0$ dB according to (2). The **A** and **B** matrix for the state transition of the mobile robot is set to

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & dt & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & v & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & dt & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 10v & 0 \\ 0 & dt \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where dt is the sampling interval set to 20 ms.

The PPO agent actor and critic neural networks are fully connected neural networks with 120 input neurons, the same as the number of input observations. This is followed by two hidden layers of 256 neurons per layer. The number of neurons in the output layer of the actor neural network is set to the number of actions to be taken which is the 10 target speed values for the 10 mobile subnetworks. Meanwhile, the critic neural network has one output neuron. We consider 1×10^6 training time steps. The number of steps per episode varies, depending on how long the last mobile subnetwork arrives at the destination. However, an episode is terminated if it exceeds 2000 steps. The PPO parameters $\gamma = 0.99$, $\epsilon = 0.2$, the actor learning rate and the critic learning rate are set to 0.0001 and 0.001 respectively. ϱ is set to a maximum value of 0.7 and decays linearly to a minimum value of 0.01 during training. $\varrho = 0.01$ is used in the execution phase. During training, we set the maximum speed of the robot to 10 m/s to keep the number of steps per episode manageable. However, during

Fig. 3: Cumulative reward per episode during the PPO training phase of the communication-aware dynamic speed control policy.

execution, we adjust the maximum speed to 2 m/s, which is more realistic for an indoor factory setting.

The cumulative rewards of the training procedure per episode are shown in Figure 3 for different penalty values K and the training converges after 8×10^5 time steps.

We compare our proposed method communication-aware dynamic speed control abbreviated as (CADSC) with: (1) a case where the target speed is fixed to the maximum, (*Max speed*) which results in the shortest arrival time. In this case, the transmit power is fixed at a maximum transmit power of 0 dBm. (2) The conventional approach of transmit power control for rate maximization [15], [16] with fixed target speed (*Max speed, Transmit power control*), where $Rate_n = \log_2(1 + SINR_n)$. The common transmit power control problem formulation is to maximize the sum of the rate subject to minimum rate constraint as in [15]. However, due to the high density of the mobile subnetworks, it is infeasible to achieve a minimum rate constraint equivalent to the SINR constraint of 0 dB for all the subnetworks. Hence, we consider maximizing a fair metric of the rate, the sum of the logarithm of the rate [16]. Hence, the transmit power control determines the transmit power that maximizes $\sum_{n=1}^N \log_{10}(Rate_n)$ subject to the maximum power of 0 dBm at every sampling interval [16]. This problem is non-convex and was solved using the non-convex optimization algorithm, Sequential Least Square Quadratic Programming (SLSQP) package of SCIPY [17].

The system model and the solution are implemented using Python.

B. Performance Evaluation and Discussion

We consider a simulation of 200 episodes involving 10 mobile subnetworks with the devices randomly deployed on a perimeter of 1 m radius with the subnetwork AP at the centre. In the case of CADSC, the PPO agent is executed to determine the target speed every 10 time step. A time step is equivalent to a sampling interval, 20 ms. At every sampling interval, an uplink transmission is initiated from the device to the transmitter, and the SINR and corresponding BLER

Fig. 4: The average arrival time for a travel distance of 25m vs the probability of achieving the minimum SINR target.

Fig. 5: The Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the achieved block error rate (BLER).

statistics are collected. Also, the travel time for the mobile subnetworks is equally monitored.

Figure 4 (a) and (b), show the average arrival time for the mobile subnetworks and the probability of achieving the minimum SINR. When the mobile subnetworks are in motion without considering communication and move at their maximum speeds, the average arrival time is shorter. However, in our proposed CADSC approach, the target speed of some mobile subnetworks may be reduced to manage density and minimize interference, resulting in a slightly increased average arrival time. Nevertheless, we also achieved a significantly higher probability of meeting the minimum SINR constraint.

When we increase the penalty (K) for not meeting the minimum SINR target in the RL reward function (7), we observe a slight increase in the average time of arrival, as well as the probability of achieving the minimum SINR. Further simulations will be necessary to analyze how the system responds to CADSC with larger K values.

In Figure (5), we present the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the BLER for two scenarios: uncontrolled motion of mobile subnetworks (with fixed transmit power and transmit power control) and controlled motion based on SINR awareness, CADSC. The analysis indicates that the BLER performance is generally poor when the mobile subnetworks move at their maximum speed (uncontrolled case). However, with CADSC, the probability of achieving low BLER is significantly higher. For instance, CADSC with $K = -10$ achieves a BLER of 10^{-8} 95% of the time. Additionally, adjusting transmit power to improve BLER performance results in only a minor gain due to the high density of mobile subnetworks moving at a constant speed.

These findings underscore the importance of integrating communication awareness into the dynamic speed control of mobile subnetworks. Managing density by adjusting the relative distance of the mobile subnetworks based on communication constraints can help mitigate interference and greatly enhance communication performance.

V. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, we have considered the problem of ensuring the minimum travel time for entities such as mobile robots, each equipped with a wireless subnetwork with tight local communication requirements. To manage the interference, we have proposed a communication-aware dynamic speed control policy using reinforcement learning. This policy leverages knowledge of the mutual interference between mobile subnetworks to adjust their target speeds, enhancing communication performance while minimizing travel time. The method shows promising results in increasing the probability of achieving the desired BLER from 75% to more than 95% while minimizing arrival time for the mobile subnetworks. Exploiting communication-aware dynamic speed control will be crucial, especially in dense scenarios with mobile subnetworks where certain radio performance requirements must be met.

Future study may consider joint path planning and inter-subnetwork interference mitigation to enable a highly spectrally efficient coexistence of both static and mobile subnetworks on the factory floor.

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